

Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Thiodipropionic Acid, Thiodiacetic Acid and Dithiodiacetic Acid Complexes with Al(III)

S. N. DUBEY*, A. SINGH, H. L. KALRA and D. M. PURI

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132-119

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The proton-ligand stability constants of thiodipropionic acid (TDPA), thiodiacetic acid (TDAA) and dithiodiacetic acid (DTDAA) and stepwise formation constants of their chelates with Al(III) have been determined in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths (0.1M, 0.2M, 0.3M and 0.4M) and temperatures (25°, 35° and 45°) using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The sodium-perchlorate solution was used to keep ionic strength constant. Thermodynamic formation constants ($\log K_n^{H=0}$) have been obtained by extrapolating the experimental values to zero ionic strength. The values of overall changes in free-energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) accompanying the complex formation have also been reported.

MERCAPTO compounds have a wide range of applications including biological, pharmaceutical, industrial and other chemical uses, and they are also well known for their complex forming tendencies. From the perusal of the literature it is evident that some work^{1,2} has been reported potentiometrically on the complexation reactions of TDPA, TDAA and DTDAA with some bivalent metal ions. No attempt, however, appears to have been made to determine the proton-ligand stability constants and formation constants of their chelates with Al(III) at different ionic strengths and temperatures. It was, therefore, considered of interest to investigate the stability of the chelates of these ligands with Al(III) potentiometrically.

Experimental

Materials: Solutions of $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck), TDPA (Evans), TDAA (Evans), DTDAA (Evans), and sodium perchlorate (Riedel) were prepared by dissolving their requisite quantities in conductivity water. Perchloric acid solution was prepared by diluting a calculated amount of the acid with conductivity water and was standardised volumetrically. The stock solution of aluminium nitrate was standardised by oxinate method.

Apparatus: A Philips pH meter model PR 9405M equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements after standardising with potassium hydrogen phthalate solution (M/20).

Procedures: All the titrations were carried out in a double-walled glass titration vessel provided with an inlet and an outlet tube using Calvin-Bjerrum^{3,4} titration technique as modified by

Irving and Rossotti⁵. The experiments were carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen.

Three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows and were titrated against carbonate-free standard caustic soda solution.

(i) $4 \times 10^{-3}M$ perchloric acid, (ii) $4 \times 10^{-3}M$ perchloric acid + $3 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand and (iii) $4 \times 10^{-3}M$ perchloric acid + $3 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand + $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ metal ion solution, such that the concentration of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate quantity of sodium perchlorate [2.0M] was added to maintain the desired ionic strengths. The three titration curves obtained were referred to as acid titration curve(A), ligand titration curve(B), and complex titration curve(C). For the sake of simplicity, titration curves obtained in Al(III)-TDPA, Al(III)-TDAA and Al(III)-DTDAA systems only at temperature 25°, $\mu=0.1M$ are given in Figure 1.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constants and stepwise formation constants were determined as follows:

The values of \bar{n}_A were evaluated at various pH values from acid and ligand titration curves using the formula of Irving and Rossotti⁶. The values of \bar{n}_A were plotted against the values of pH (Fig. 2; temp. = 25°, $\mu=0.1M$). From this graph the values of proton-ligand stability constants were computed using different computational techniques⁶. The values are given in Table 1.

* To whom correspondence should be made.

Fig. 1. Titration curves (Temp. = 25°C, $\mu = 0.1M$)

- Acid
- ⊕ Ligand(TDPA)
- △ Al(III)—TDPA
- Ligand TDAA
- △ Al(III)—TDAA
- Ligand(DTDAA)
- ▲ Al(III)—DTDAA

Fig. 2. Plot of \bar{n}_A versus pH (Temp = 25°C, $\mu = 0.1M$)

- DTDAA
- ⊕ TDAA
- TDPA

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TDPA, TDAA AND DTDAA AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS AND TEMPERATURES

Sl. No.	Ligand used	Constants	Temperature						
			25°				35°		45°
			Ionic Strength (μ)						
			0.1M	0.2M	0.3M	0.4M	0.1M	0.1M	
1.	TDPA	Log K_1^H	4.74	4.56	4.51	4.43	4.82	4.96	
		Log K_2^H	3.64	3.74	3.71	3.69	3.75	3.94	
		Log β_2^H	8.38	8.30	8.22	8.12	8.57	8.90	
2.	TDAA	Log K_1^H	4.11	4.07	4.03	3.98	4.21	4.36	
		Log K_2^H	2.94	2.90	2.85	2.80	3.02	3.15	
		Log β_2^H	7.05	6.98	6.89	6.77	7.24	7.51	
3.	DTDAA	Log K_1^H	3.87	3.85	3.75	3.68	3.95	4.08	
		Log K_2^H	2.72	2.65	2.60	2.54	2.76	2.94	
		Log β_2^H	6.59	6.50	6.36	6.22	6.70	7.01	

The stepwise stability constants of the metal complexes were determined with the help of formation curves (\bar{n} versus pL; Fig. 3; temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1M$) using various computational methods⁶. The values of \bar{n} , the average number of ligands attached per metal ion, and the free ligand exponent pL were calculated from ligand and complex titration curves

using the formula of Irving and Rossotti⁵. The values are given in Table 2.

Thermodynamic stability constants, given in Table 2, were obtained by extrapolation of experimentally determined formation constants to zero ionic strength.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Al(III) COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS AND TEMPERATURES

Sl. No.	Ligand used	Constants	Temperature						
			25°				35°		45°
			Ionic Strength (μ)						
			0.1M	0.2M	0.3M	0.4M	0.1M	0.1M	
1.	TDPA	Log K_1	3.99	3.79	3.53	3.39	4.04	4.13	
		Log K_2	3.21	3.09	3.02	2.97	3.31	3.44	
		Log β_2	7.20	6.88	6.55	6.36	7.34	7.57	
2.	TDAA	Log K_1	3.72	3.59	3.38	3.27	4.08	4.23	
		Log K_2	3.08	3.04	2.98	2.92	3.13	3.19	
		Log β_2	6.80	6.63	6.36	6.19	7.21	7.42	
3.	DTDAA	Log K_1	3.39	3.30	3.17	3.02	3.64	3.82	
		Log K_2	2.98	2.94	2.90	2.85	3.01	3.10	
		Log β_2	6.37	6.25	6.06	5.87	6.65	6.92	

The values of thermodynamic formation constants ($\log K_{11}^{\mu=0}$) thus obtained for Al(III)-TDPA, Al(III)-TDAA and Al(III)-DTDAA chelates at 25° are 4.19, 3.27 ; 3.90, 3.15 and 3.54, 3.02 respectively.

 Fig. 3. Plot of \bar{n} versus pL (Temp = 25°C, $\mu = 0.1M$)

- DTDAA
- ⊕ TDAA
- TDPA

The values of the overall changes in free-energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) for the complexes, given in Table 3, were calculated using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Al(III) COMPLEXES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Ligand used	T, °C	$-\Delta G^\circ$	ΔH°	ΔS°
		K cal mole ⁻¹	K cal mole ⁻¹	Cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
TDPA	25	9.82		59.66
	35	10.94	7.96	59.41
	45	11.01		59.65
TDAA	25	9.27		75.97
	35	10.16	13.37	76.39
	45	10.80		76.00
DTDAA	25	8.63		69.06
	35	9.37	11.90	69.05
	45	10.07		69.08

equation⁷ given below :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \int_n \beta.$$

$$\frac{d(\log \beta)}{d(1/T)} = \frac{-\Delta H^\circ}{4.576}$$

and

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T}$$

The values of ΔH° were calculated graphically using the above isobar equation, i.e., by plotting $\log \beta$ values at different temperatures as a function of $(1/T)$ and equating the gradient of this plot with

$$\frac{-\Delta H^\circ}{4.576}.$$

The values of protonation constants show a decreasing trend with increase in ionic strength and increasing trend with increase in temperature. Ligands TDPA, TDAA and DTDAA seem to act as terdentate^{1,8}. A comparison of the stepwise formation constants indicates that the stability increases with increase in temperature, i.e., higher temperature is favourable for complex formation. At a particular temperature, the values decrease in the order TDPA > TDAA > DTDAA.

The chelates of Al(III) with TDPA, TDAA and DTDAA, are all formed spontaneously as evidenced by the negative values of ΔG° . The positive values of ΔH° ensures that the reaction is endothermic.

The relatively small ΔH° values compared with the large values of ΔS° indicate entropy as the principal driving force for the formation of the metal complexes in aqueous solution, i.e., increase in randomness in system will increase the stability of complex because entropy is a solvent property. Species in water solutions are surrounded by a cloud of water molecules with a geometry different from that of bulk water. The complex has a greater radius and reduced charge as compared to the reactants, and therefore, water molecules will be released in association reactions. It was pointed out by Williams⁹ that usually where a high entropy of reaction was observed, it involved a combination of positive and negative ions. Combination of a metal ion with a negative ligand always involves the displacement of water molecules, which then become part of the solvent. Since the water molecules bound to the metal ion are highly distorted and oriented, their entropy is very low. Thus any process which releases water molecules from this type of strain, results in a favourable increase in entropy. The values of ΔS° are positive in all the systems,

indicating that entropy is favourable for complex formation.

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